

STUDY OF THE NUTRITIONAL AND ENERGETIC VALUE OF INGREDIENTS IN DATE-BASED PUREES FOR CHILDREN'S FOOD

A.A Nurmukhamedov

teacher of Gulistan state university

axmadnurmuxamedov@gmail.com +99897-275-07-09

S.K Kuzibekov

dotsent of Gulistan state university

kuzibekovsardor27@gmail.com +99897-275-07-09

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ABSTRACT

The nutritional and energetic value of the ingredients in date-based puree has been studied and analyzed

Introduction. It is known that proper nutrition for preschool and primary school-age children is an important factor in ensuring the necessary nutritional status of children, preventing diseases, and maintaining health.

For toddlers, the development and implementation of recipes based on melon puree are carried out using models, including creating a product model according to specified quality indicators, selecting and justifying the initial ingredients (raw materials), and justifying the formation of the product in accordance with nutritional and physiological value criteria.

It should be noted that developed products must correspond to traditional organoleptic properties, which ensures their consumer appeal and satiety.

The composition of a multicomponent puree, containing functional components such as glucose, dietary fiber, vitamin C, P, β -carotene, iron, and potassium, is based on the principles of food combinatorics, taking into account the child's body's daily needs.

Literature review. The development of age-inappropriate chronic diseases in children is often associated with disorders in their nutritional status. This is primarily explained by an imbalance in the diet - excessive consumption of sugar, an overabundance of animal fats, and conversely, a deficiency of essential micronutrients. This situation creates the ground for disruptions in metabolic processes and the development of various pathologies.

It has been scientifically proven that a deficiency of each micronutrient is associated with a specific spectrum of diseases. For example, iron deficiency is linked to anemia, iodine deficiency to thyroid diseases, and insufficient intake of vitamins, macro- and micronutrients, and dietary fiber is closely related to insulin resistance and overweight problems, which can be observed at any age [1].

An analysis of the level of vitamin provision among children of different ages shows that polyhypovitaminosis - a simultaneous deficiency of several vitamins - is widespread in many cases. It has been established that the development of this condition is mainly due to insufficient consumption of ascorbic acid and B-group vitamins [2,3].

A deficiency of a number of vitamins has been observed among preschool and primary school-age children: Vitamin C - 38%, B₂ - 79%, B₆ - 64%, Vitamin E - 22%, β-carotene - 84%. Even in the summer season, i.e., during the period of highest consumption of fruits and vegetables, ascorbic acid deficiency was recorded in 65% of children, vitamin B₂ - in 54%, vitamin B₆ - in 35%, and folic acid - in 70%. In 20-40% of children, vitamin deficiency reached the level of severe deficiency [3,4].

Furthermore, iron deficiency in children was identified in 20-30%, calcium deficiency in 25-30%, iodine deficiency in 20-75%, and a deficiency of essential ω-3 group fatty acids in over 50% of children [5].

Conducted scientific research also confirms the importance of dietary fiber in children's nutrition. They play an important role not only in the prevention and treatment of obesity but also in reducing blood cholesterol levels, which significantly lowers the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases in children [6].

Analysis and results. To study the nutritional and energetic value of the developed purees, the content of their main nutrients - proteins, carbohydrates, organic acids, and dietary fibers - was determined. Based on the results obtained, the energetic value was calculated in accordance with the procedure established by TR TS 022/2011 "Rules for Labeling Food Products."

The following conversion coefficients were used to determine the energetic value: Proteins - 4 kcal/g (17 kJ/g); carbohydrates, including mono- and disaccharides - 4 kcal/g (17 kJ/g); organic acids - 3 kcal/g (13 kJ/g); dietary fibers - 2 kcal/g (8 kJ/g).

Table 1 presents the content of the main nutrients in the developed purees, as well as their energetic value.

Table 1

Content of main nutrients in the purees and energetic value of the produced purees

Name of Main Nutrient	Amount of Essential Nutrients, g/100 g		
	Date, Apple & Pumpkin	Date, Apple & Carrot	Date, Apple, Carrot & Pumpkin
Carbohydrates	12,63	12,66	12,07
Proteins	0,93	0,95	1,03
Dietary Fiber	3,89	3,87	3,78
Organic Acids	0,34	0,39	0,30
Energetic Value:			
Kcal	31,8	34,3	32,3
kJ	133,1	143,4	135,5

During the research, the nutrient composition of three types of mixed purees developed on a date base was analyzed and their energetic value was calculated. As can be seen from the table, carbohydrates predominate as the main energy source in all purees. In the date-apple-pumpkin puree, the carbohydrate content was 12.63 g/100 g, in date-apple-carrot puree - 12.66 g/100 g, and in date-apple-carrot-pumpkin puree - 12.07 g/100 g. These values indicate a stable presence of carbohydrates consisting of easily digestible natural sugars, which are important in children's nutrition.

The protein content also varies depending on the mixed raw material composition. The highest indicator was recorded in the date, apple, carrot, and pumpkin mixture, amounting to 1.03 g/100 g. This is formed due to natural plant proteins in vegetables and fruits and serves to support growth processes necessary for the child's body. The protein content in date-apple-carrot puree is 0.95 g, and in date-apple-pumpkin puree - 0.93 g/100 g, which is explained by differences in the recipes.

The amount of dietary fibers (dietary fibers) was sufficiently high in all samples, amounting to 3.89 g, 3.87 g, and 3.78 g/100 g, respectively. The mixture of pectin, cellulose, and hemicellulose preserved in dates, apples, carrots, and pumpkin has been scientifically proven to improve children's digestive system, stabilize intestinal microflora, and aid in the elimination of toxins. Furthermore, these amounts comply with the requirements of TR TS 021/2011.

The amount of organic acids ranged from 0.30 to 0.39 g/100 g, primarily formed due to the natural malic acid and citric acid present in apples and carrots. These acids have the property of optimizing digestive processes in the child's body, improving nutrient absorption, and providing a mild antioxidant effect.

When calculating the total energetic value, 31.8 kcal or 133.1 kJ were recorded for date-apple-pumpkin puree, 34.3 kcal or 143.1 kJ for date-apple-carrot puree, and 32.3 kcal or 135.5 kJ for date-apple-carrot-pumpkin puree. These values correspond to the recommended energy balance for children, indicating that the products are safe and physiologically appropriate for inclusion in the diet.

Conclusion. These results confirm the balanced nature of the composition, the minimal difference in energetic and nutritional indicators among all purees, and that each recipe is developed in accordance with the age and physiological needs of children. Also, the high nutritional value of the purees is formed through the natural composition of dates, carrots, pumpkin, and apple, indicating that no additional artificial fortification is required.

The advantage of date-based purees is precisely manifested in their richness in β -carotene, vitamin C, natural pectins, and polyphenols. Therefore, these purees can be recommended as functional products in children's nutrition.

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